

PURE COVIDATA: AN AUTOMATED SONIFICATION OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC'S RECENT STATE

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ABSTRACT

Pure Covidata is a project which aims to artistically and informatively represent daily updated COVID-19 case and death data through synthesized sound using Pure Data (Pd) [1]. We define a spectrum of *abrasiveness* as a model for a sonic representation of the pandemic's state. Towards its realization, we present two sonification strategies that we refer to as *timbral* and *intervallic*, and which we implement in Pd by means of FM and subtractive synthesis, respectively. *Pure Covidata* was created in the context of the *Streaaam* experimental audio streaming server [2], which retrieves the underlying data and broadcasts the resulting audio in an automated fashion as one of many stream programs on a set schedule. This paper discusses the sonification strategies and technical implementation of *Pure Covidata*, whereas we plan to describe details of the project more pertinent to *Streaaam*, such as pedagogical considerations and data retrieval and parsing, in another publication. We also reflect on how the sonification of data generated after the project's implementation phase has since informed adjustments of the sonification algorithms and discuss plans for future work, including a listening experiment for evaluating the project's informational, emotional, and aesthetic impact.

1. INTRODUCTION

Pure Covidata aims to produce an ongoing daily sonification of data specifically related to COVID-19 in an artistic and emotionally impactful way, independently of any human intervention. It was created as a response to the first author's observed dearth of emotionally impactful representations of the state of the COVID-19 pandemic. The goal of the project was to create an artistic sonification of the pandemic's current and recent state that would be affecting, of artistic value, and easy to digest. The *abrasiveness* model introduced in section 2 aims to serve as a vehicle for realizing the intended emotional impact.

It bears acknowledging that this project carries with it an ethical responsibility not to misrepresent the gravity of the numbers used to generate its output. Each sonified figure represents either a number of lives lost to the COVID-19 pandemic or a number of people who suffered the illness, often with life-altering consequences. Our hope is that the results can, to some extent, help to elucidate to listeners how impactful the pandemic has been and continues to be at the time of writing.

1.1. Overview of sonification process

Data to be sonified is drawn from Narrativa's *COVID-19 Tracking Project* API [3], which was available until early June 2022 and incorporated data from Johns Hopkins University for the United States [4]. Shell scripts using the `curl`¹ and `jq`² commands are scheduled using `cron` in order to aggregate daily numbers of new COVID-19 cases and deaths in Cook County, Illinois – as well as the percentages by which their respective totals have increased relative to the previous day – into two text files, one for each dataset.

A Pd patch then uses an FM synthesis module that plays individual note events for cases, and a subtractive synthesis module that plays continuous four-note chords for deaths (cf., sections 4 and 5). The raw data is mapped to a variety of parameters within these two modules, including pitch, envelope duration, modulation index, filter frequency, and panning. Thus, the higher the value of each data point, the higher pitched and more 'abrasive' (cf., sections 2 and 3) the sonification for that day's data will be.

The complete Pd patch and the set of case and death figures used for the project, as well as an audio file that is representative of its output, are available at this URL:

https://bit.ly/pure_covidata

1.2. Research context & similar projects

The *Pure Covidata* project is embedded in a research context that concerns itself with the sonification of scientific data [5] in general, and of COVID-19 data in particular. A number of similar sonification projects have been devised since the onset of the pandemic. One such study by Rebelo [6] employs sonification methods similar to those of this project: it interprets total global figures of cases and deaths between late January and late March 2020 as frequencies of a sine and sawtooth wave generator, respectively. Every time these values exceed 20 kHz, which in the given time-frame occurs only for cases, a woodblock sound signals that the frequency is being wrapped down into the range of human hearing by subtracting 20,000 from the case figure. While such a direct mapping of data to pitch is informative for these earliest days of the pandemic, it cannot account for later waves, where worldwide cases and deaths total in the hundreds of millions, and even daily cases can exceed hundreds of thousands.

Martin's *SARS Coronavirus Replicase Sonification* [7] was created and performed in Edinburgh in early 2020, even before the

¹<https://curl.se>

²<https://stedolan.github.io/jq>

UK’s first COVID-19 fatality. Rather than case and death data, it uses the “protein sequence of the replicase polyprotein lab from the SARS coronavirus” as a dataset. The piece employs Cycling ’74’s *Max* program to sonify this data using percussion samples, a bass synthesizer, and a “distorted lead” using a “hydrophobicity scale” [8]. The sonification strategies employed in this project also resemble those of *Pure Covidata*, but the work requires a human performer to “manipulate the sound as it is synthesized,” whereas *Pure Covidata* runs on the *Streaaam* server in an entirely automated fashion.

Another related project by Falk and Dykstra [9] does not utilize COVID-19 data but conveys information to security operators about potential cyber threats through a continuous sonification of network data. Like in *Pure Covidata*, sonic aesthetics play a key role insofar as one of the goals is not to overwhelm operators with unpleasant or overly detailed sonifications. In contrast to our project, the framework accounts for both discrete and continuous data. Discrete data, such as intrusion detection alarms or user login events, is signified by adding “intrusive noise” or harmonic tension to the music already being played. Changes to continuous data, such as network traffic volume, are translated to adjustments of the musical dynamics or the addition or removal of individual melodic lines. Such strategies reflect *Pure Covidata*’s model of translating higher case and death figures to more ‘abrasive’ sonifications (cf., section 2). However, while Falk and Dykstra prefer approaches that minimize listening fatigue, this is less of a concern for *Pure Covidata*, where listeners can tune out at any time they wish.

2. ABRASIVENESS MODEL OF SONIFICATION

In the process of determining how to sonify COVID-19 statistics, the main goals were:

1. for the sonification to informatively reflect the underlying data, and
2. for the output to come across, to some extent, as an intentionally crafted musical piece despite its generative nature.

The emphasis of *Pure Covidata*, being primarily an artistic project, leans more heavily on the latter of these two criteria. That being said, the raw data does paint a clear picture: higher reported numbers of new cases and deaths reflect a worse, more alarming state of the pandemic, whereas lower numbers reflect a better, more optimistic state. Thus, the goal was to reflect these patterns sonically and musically.

To establish a nomenclature with which to describe these aesthetic intentions, we will refer to the quality *abrasiveness* to describe the sonic representation of higher case and death figures, somewhat reflecting (albeit in a less formalized manner) Collins’ analysis of pieces from the musical genre of *harsh noise* in terms of features such as “perceptual loudness, transientness [and] sensory dissonance” [10]. These features, which are also present in those sounds in our project that represent higher COVID-19 case or death figures, can be said to characterize an abrasive sound texture [11], a continuum whose opposing end can be described as comparatively *gentle*.

Thus, this textural spectrum of *abrasiveness* represents for our project a model for sonifying data whose cause for concern is proportional to its magnitude: more ‘alarming’ data composed of

higher figures manifest in a sonic form intended to be more abrasive to the listener, while lower figures are represented as being less abrasive, or ‘gentler.’

3. SONIFICATION STRATEGIES

Having two different sets of (case- versus death-related) data at our disposal afforded us the opportunity to musically explore the textural continuum between abrasive and gentle sounds, as defined in section 2, through two distinct approaches.

The timbral approach incorporates *timbral inharmonicity* as a strategy for achieving abrasiveness. It consists of individual note events whose spectra are determined by the data, ranging from single-frequency tones to note events of varying (and at times extreme) degrees of (in)harmonicity, as well as variable envelope times for amplitude and other parameters.

The intervallic approach, in contrast, employs the abrasiveness model in the form of *intervallic dissonance*, incorporating the relationship between multiple continuous, concurrent tones arranged into four-note chords. The root note and intervals within each chord are determined by the COVID-19 data, according to a conflation of two five-limit scales [12] shown in table 1. The chords play throughout the piece and serve as a musically grounded backdrop over which the relatively abstract timbral ‘lead’ can be allowed to pull focus.

In either approach, the sonic and harmonic texture of the resultant musical output is determined so as to reflect the magnitude of the figures being represented, higher numbers being associated with periods of crisis and thus resulting in timbres and intervals intended to be more abrasive and alarming to the average listener. It was intuitively decided to use the timbral approach to represent case data, and the intervallic approach for death figures.

3.1. Timbral approach (case data)

In our mapping strategy, case data determines both the FM carrier frequency and how aggressively the carrier is modulated (cf., section 4.1). This strategy introduces varying degrees of inharmonicity into the output spectrum, more modulation lending it a more metallic and abrasive timbre. While inharmonicity does not necessarily constitute a more abrasive sound [13], a pure sine tone sounds arguably less abrasive than a timbre that due to runaway inharmonicity exhibits no discernible pitch.

Keeping in mind the human auditory system’s well-documented sensitivity to frequencies around 2 kHz to 4 kHz [14, 15], our output spectrum’s perceived abrasiveness is further aided by increasing toward that range the carrier frequency and, by proxy, its sideband frequencies. Akin to the natural urgency to escape or turn off the incessant ringing of a piercing alarm, a creative decision was made to increase amplitude envelope duration of note events to further contribute to the sonification’s subjective abrasiveness and thereby indicate higher figures.

Thus, a tone representative of more alarming data would present as a long, metallic-sounding, high-pitched and, as such, more ‘abrasive’ timbre, whereas lower figures translate to shorter, quieter, more melodic, and thus ‘gentler’ timbres.

Interval	Ratio
Perfect unison	1 : 1
Minor second	16 : 15
Major second	9 : 8
Minor third	6 : 5
Major third	5 : 4
Perfect fourth	4 : 3
Tritone	25 : 18
Perfect fifth	3 : 2
Minor sixth	8 : 5
Major sixth	5 : 3
Minor seventh	16 : 9
Major seventh	15 : 8
Perfect octave	2 : 1

Table 1: Frequency ratios of the five-limit tuning system [12] used in the *Pure Covidata* Pd patch.

3.2. Intervallic approach (death data)

In the intervallic approach, the perceptual abrasiveness of the musical output is determined by the perceived consonance or dissonance as determined by the ratios of a chord’s root to three additional notes above it. Following a basic Pythagorean theory of consonance, we define more consonant intervals as those employing simpler frequency ratios [16], in the simplest cases an octave and a perfect fifth (cf., table 1). In terms of texture, these intervals are perceived as being gentler; “relaxing, calming, of wellbeing, and of resolution” [17]. It follows that intervals considered more dissonant, composed of more complex frequency ratios, would likely be perceived as relatively tense and thus more ‘abrasive’.

As a first approximation, it can be observed that more intervallic dissonance tends to result from smaller intervals, such as a minor or major second. Thus, *Pure Covidata* employs an *inverse* relationship between the figures for deaths and the interval between each chord’s root and successive notes, such that both the root note’s fundamental frequency and the multipliers of the fundamental which determine the pitch of each note in the chord above it are determined by the death data, the smallest possible interval (associated with *higher* numbers) being a minor second and the largest a major seventh. The same pairing of higher frequencies with longer note durations described in section 3.1 is employed in this approach as well.

Thus, higher death-related figures yield long, high-pitched, abrasive chords whose intervals are uncomfortably close together, while lower numbers result in chords shorter in duration, in which the notes are both lower in frequency and separated by larger musical intervals.

4. CHOICE OF SOUND SYNTHESIS TECHNIQUES

To implement the two approaches, appropriate synthesis techniques had to be selected for each, keeping in mind the limited number of parameters available for sonification. For the timbral approach, an ideal technique would be one capable of producing a wide variety of timbres using few parameters. The intervallic approach, in contrast, required a technique also capable of producing a wide sonic palette using limited components, yet more conducive to providing a relatively grounded, consistent musical backdrop for the

timbrally more abstract lead.

4.1. FM synthesis (timbral approach; case data)

For the timbral approach representing case data, FM synthesis [18] was an obvious choice. Using FM, it is easy to drastically vary the texture of a timbre to generate note events ranging from pure sine tones to those more closely resembling white noise. *Pure Covidata*’s FM module is deliberately based on a relatively simple design resembling Chowning’s (with some exceptions). It uses a single envelope generator, carrier oscillator, and modulating oscillator, and offers three well-known FM parameters: carrier frequency, harmonicity, and modulation index. Despite its simplicity, this design is able to employ much of FM’s range of capabilities by adjusting the number and distance of a given carrier’s sideband frequencies with limited input, providing the wide palette of textures required to timbrally represent the input data.

4.2. Subtractive synthesis (intervallic approach; death data)

For the intervallic approach representing death data, the requirement was to select a familiar synthesis technique that could be efficiently implemented in Pure Data and would yield more timbrally accessible sonifications than the relatively chaotic, shapeshifting FM lead. This would allow the data to communicate more effectively through the notes being played and the relationships between them than through their respective spectromorphologies [11]. Subtractive synthesis proved to be such a technique, easily implementable in Pd with sawtooth wave generators, band pass filters, and low frequency oscillators, the sonic output thereof being timbrally diverse yet familiar enough to yield focus to the less predictable FM lead when necessary.

5. IMPLEMENTATION IN PURE DATA (PD)

Figure 1: [pd caseText] subpatch used in *Pure Covidata*

In the context of the fully automated *Streaaam* server [2] on which it currently resides, *Pure Covidata* is initiated at set times within

the broadcast schedule. Immediately upon loading the patch, the two text files, `caseData.txt` and `deathData.txt` are read in separate subpatches using Pd's native `[textfile]` object,³ which outputs one line of the selected text file as a list whenever it receives a bang message (cf., figure 1 for case data). These text files contain the data accumulated over time for daily new `cases` and `deaths` and the percentage increase of their respective totals relative to those of the previous day (`caseIncrease` and `deathIncrease`). In order to distribute the data chronologically, a `[metro]` object regularly triggers the `[textfile]` object to output the next day's case or death figures and route them to their respective destinations in the FM and subtractive synthesis modules.

As an example, the following entries for case and death data from these two `.txt` files reflect the newly confirmed numbers of cases and deaths for February 22, 2022, as well as a 0.18% and 0.37% increase of their respective totals in comparison to the previous day.

```
cases 2025
caseIncrease 0.0018321431188776938

deaths 52
deathIncrease 0.0037453183520599342
```

5.1. Case data (FM synthesis; timbral approach)

For case data, a fixed metronome time interval of 1750 ms was initially chosen to be aesthetically optimal. However, as a result of the unpredictable nature of the project (cf., sec 6.1), the metronome time was changed to be the same as that used for death data (cf. section 5.2) to better sync the two modules chronologically. Because FM tone durations are variable (resulting in some tone overlapping), it was necessary to incorporate polyphony by including six separate FM modules, to which the data is alternately routed according to an automatically prepended number between 0 and 5 (cf., figure 1). Inside each FM module is an FM synthesis generator and an ADSR envelope generator. The FM generator's carrier frequency and harmonicity value are determined by the number of `cases` and its percentage increase (`caseIncrease`), respectively, each scaled to appropriate ranges. The ADSR envelope both attenuates the FM synthesizer's output level (its maximum level determined by `caseIncrease` scaled up by a factor of 500) and modulates its modulation index, which, together with harmonicity and carrier frequency, determines the depth of the frequency modulation. In the interest of retaining both informational and entertainment value upon repeated listening, the envelope's attack, decay, sustain, and release times are randomized within a range whose maximum possible value is the number of `cases` (representing milliseconds). As such, these parameters are *informed* by the data without being directly determined by it.

5.2. Death data (subtractive synthesis; intervallic approach)

For death data, the `[metro]` speed (and thus the duration of each chord) is determined for each step by the corresponding entry for `deaths`, multiplied by 150 (e.g. 52 deaths translate to

7800 ms). Because there is no overlap between separate data entries, there is no need for the polyphony as implemented in the `[pd caseText]` subpatch. Inside the subtractive module are four subtractive synthesis generators (cf., figure 2), each with two `[phasor~]` sawtooth oscillators whose frequency is determined by the number of `deaths`, and whose frequency offset is determined by the `deathIncrease`. Each `[phasor~]` feeds into a `[vcf~]` bandpass filter whose frequency is also determined by the number of `deaths` as well as modulated by a low-frequency oscillator. A `[line]` object generates a portamento effect to transition between chords.

Following the chord's root, each successive note's frequency is determined by a Pd abstraction that takes as input a multiple of `deathIncrease`, rounded to the nearest integer, and outputs the required multiplier for the root frequency according to the five-limit scale shown in table 1. In accordance with our inverse mapping strategy for the intervallic approach discussed in section 3.2, higher `deathIncrease` values are mapped to *smaller* note intervals. The multipliers of the percentage increase for the non-root notes are 3000, 6000, and 8000, intended to ensure a chord composed of four distinct notes. For aesthetic purposes, a 5000 ms fade is applied to the beginning and end of the module's output.

5.3. Global effects: Panning, reverb, ducking, quit

Pan values determined by the case and death percentage increases are used to provide space and atmosphere for the piece, as well as a stereo reverb effect using Pd's `[rev1~]` abstraction. Similarly, a stereo ducker abstraction is used to attenuate the subtractive module's output relative to that of the FM modules to draw focus to the FM lead when appropriate. For additional limiting (the need for which is described in 6.1), if the RMS amplitude of the combined audio output exceeds certain thresholds, the output of the FM module (more often than not the responsible party when the output gets out of hand) is attenuated. Finally, in order for the *Streamaam* server to know when to move on to the next program, the same RMS envelope follower is used to quit Pd shortly after the audio output has ceased due to the patch's 'arrival' at the most recent available data.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The *Pure Covidata* project was intended from the outset to continue aggregating and sonifying COVID-19 data beyond the project's implementation phase, which was concluded in early December of 2021. Since then, about six months' worth of new data have been accumulated and provide the basis for some first reflections on the chosen sonification strategies.

6.1. Post-implementation adjustments to the sonification

As the pandemic continued to supply *Pure Covidata* with fresh – and at times unexpected – data to be sonified after the project's initial implementation, the need for some adjustments to the sonification algorithms became apparent.

For example, by the time the aggregated data had amassed to around 100 days' worth of entries, the previous constant metronome value for case data of 1750 ms yielded an output in which the sonification thereof ended well before that of death data. The surge in cases and deaths as a result of the Omicron variant in the winter of 2021–2022 [19] may be partly to blame for this phenomenon, as

³Throughout this paper, we shall identify Pd objects, abstractions, and subpatches by enclosing their names in square brackets, a notation that is commonly used within the Pd community.

Figure 2: [subOsc~] Pd abstraction used in the *Pure Covidata* project

the metronome value for the subtractive module was from the out-set variable and determined directly by the number of new deaths (cf., section 5.2).

The same surge in January 2022 led to another unforeseen consequence: The audio output of the FM module for case data became untenably loud. This issue gave way to the attenuation strategy for the FM module as described in section 5.3.

6.2. Reflections on the chord generation algorithm

Upon listening to the project’s output, another observation is that, while the musicality of the subtractive module representing the intervallic method is a grounding and welcome contrast to the abstract and unpredictable FM module exemplifying the timbral method, the former’s output is somewhat less intuitively symbolic of its numeric input (death data). That is, whereas the FM lead for case data varies wildly in timbre and becomes quite noticeably more abrasive (long, loud, high-pitched, lacking a discernible pitch) the higher its input values, the subtractive module’s output perhaps requires at least a basic understanding of its mechanisms in order to properly associate it with its input, detracting somewhat

from the intended emotional impact.

This is likely owed in part to the implementation strategy described in section 3.2, whereby higher figures (deathIncrease, specifically) yield chords ‘whose intervals are uncomfortably close together’. In its current state, it is uncommon for any generated chord to sound especially consonant, regardless of the magnitude of its associated values for deaths and deathIncrease.

A more robust sonification strategy could aim at generating chords along a consonance-dissonance continuum that is more systematically informed by psychoacoustic research, for example as outlined in [20], with the goal of producing a more intuitive and emotionally impactful sonification of this data.

6.3. API availability and future data retrieval

On June 3, 2022, citing consistently lower case and death rates, Narrativa formally concluded their *COVID-19 Tracking Project*, as well as the API that went along with it and upon which *Pure Covidata*’s functionality depended [21].

We have therefore recently started to implement a script that retrieves the data directly from its original source, an online repos-

itory by the Center for Systems Science and Engineering (CSSE) at Johns Hopkins University, which at the time of writing continues to receive daily updates.⁴ Since the data is published there in CSV rather than JSON format (and in a ‘rawer’ form than what the Narrativa API used to provide), further work will be required before this process can once again be automated on the server.

6.4. Evaluation of sonification strategies

As another next step, we hope to conduct a descriptive study [22] of the project’s goals defined in section 2 with a representative group of subjects, to better understand *Pure Covidata*’s subjective value as a work of sonic art and its informational value as a tool for gaining insight as to the current and recent state of the COVID-19 pandemic.

To that end, we plan to design a suitable listening experiment to address yet-to-be-refined research questions such as:

- What sensations or emotions did the piece yield or convey? Can listeners identify any specific moments that are more affecting than others?
- Are there moments or periods in the sonification in which spikes in the underlying data are apparent? Using the provided explanation, is it possible to guess whether the spikes belong to case or death data?
- Can the project successfully stand alone as a sonic art work, without additional context about the nature of the sonified data or the sonification methods employed?

We envision a two-stage experiment where in the first stage, participants would be exposed to the project’s sonified output without additional context. In the second stage, participants would be provided with an explanation as to the sonification strategies of the project – that the project sonifies COVID-19 data; that cases are represented by discrete (and sometimes overlapping) note events; that deaths are represented by continuous four-note chords; and that the magnitude of the data used in each module is intended to correlate to the perceived abrasiveness of the resulting sonification.

Surveys would accompany both stages, using test methods such as multiple matching, short answer questions, or multiple choice questions [23] to determine whether the listener’s subjective experience aligns with its goals and intentions as outlined in sections 1 and 2. In this context we intend to evaluate the suitability of direct elicitation methods such as free-choice profiling, repertory grid technique, and flash profile [24]. After a quantitative and qualitative analysis [22], the results could thereafter be used to inform further modifications to the sonification strategies and algorithms.

6.5. Alternative presentation formats

Pure Covidata, in its current state as part of an automated audio stream, has thus far not needed to concern itself with direct user interaction, as it retrieves and sonifies current data in a fully autonomous fashion according to set parameters and schedules. A future iteration of *Pure Covidata* might exist in a format independent of the *Streaaam* server for which it was initially conceived.

An example which would maximize the accessibility of the framework in terms of both reach and ease of use might be a web interface or app. Therein, a geographical location in the form of a

U. S. county and a range of dates may be input into a GUI in the form of a drop-down menu and text boxes, respectively, in order to provide listeners with a more personalized output. For more direct sonic interaction, one could include the ability to adjust parameters such as reverb decay, time constants, and the various manifestations of data scalars in real time using graphical objects such as sliders or knobs.

Incorporating these means of interactivity to personalize the framework’s input and output might yield a more informative sonification tailored to the concerns and curiosities of the listener in the case of the former, and a more aesthetically stimulating and engaging sonification in the case of the latter.

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⁴<https://github.com/CSSEGISandData/COVID-19/>

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